

A Comparative Study of Clonidine Doses with Bupivacaine in Spinal Anaesthesia: Analgesic Efficacy and Side Effect Profile

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Abstract:

Background: Spinal anaesthesia is widely acknowledged as a safe and effective method for providing anaesthetic in surgeries involving the infraumbilical region and lower limbs. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the efficacy of two different doses of intrathecal clonidine as an adjunct to bupivacaine for spinal anaesthesia.

Methods: This randomized double-blinded study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology at our tertiary care hospital from February 2023 to June 2024. Seventy patients were divided into: Group I and Group II. Postoperative analgesia was evaluated using the visual analog scale with a 0-10 cm range. The hemodynamic parameters and the number of significant events (bradycardia, hypotension, sedation) were documented and analyzed for comparison.

Results: The mean time for the onset of sensory and motor block in group II was less than group I (p<0.05). The duration of analgesia was significantly prolonged in Group II. The mean VAS score of Group II was lower at every follow-up in Group II. Minimal side effects observed in both the groups which was non significant.

Conclusion: The administration of spinal anaesthesia utilizing 0.5% bupivacaine heavy combined with 30 mcg of clonidine noted superior efficacy as an adjuvant in achieving an earlier onset of sensory and motor blockade during surgery, as well as extending the duration of effective postoperative analgesia, in comparison to the use of 15 mcg of clonidine.

Keywords: Spinal Anaesthesia, Bupivacaine, Intrathecal Clonidine, Infraumbilical Surgeries.

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Introduction

Spinal anaesthesia is widely acknowledged as a safe and effective method for providing anaesthesia in surgeries involving the infraumbilical region and lower limbs. This technique allows for the induction of profound and consistent sensory analgesia and motor blockade with a minimal volume of medication, resulting in negligible systemic pharmacological effects.[1] In contrast, epidural anaesthesia necessitates a larger volume of local anaesthetic, which can lead to pharmacologically active systemic blood levels, potentially causing side effects that are infrequently associated with spinal anaesthesia.[2] Bupivacaine, due to its pharmacological properties, exerts a stabilizing effect on all excitable membranes and offers a distinct clinical profile of nerve blockade compared to lignocaine. It is four times more potent than lignocaine and achieves a more significant sensory block; however, its duration of action is relatively short, typically lasting between

75 to 150 minutes. The drawbacks of bupivacaine include a slower onset of action and a reduced motor block.[3]

Opioid analgesics, when administered into the subarachnoid or epidural space, provide strong and prolonged analgesia without significant autonomic changes, loss of motor function, or sensory impairment beyond pain.[4] Nonetheless, they can lead to serious adverse effects such as delayed and unpredictable respiratory depression, postoperative nausea and vomiting, pruritus, urinary retention, and activation of herpes labialis. Various adjuvants, including fentanyl, clonidine, ketamine, morphine, and buprenorphine, have been utilized to extend the effects of intrathecal bupivacaine, thereby prolonging the duration of analgesia.[5]

Clonidine, in particular, has been employed by anaesthesiologists as an adjuvant to enhance perioperative cardiovascular stability,

sympathoadrenal balance, and both general and regional anaesthesia. It is an α_2 agonist, which interacts with adrenoceptors located in the spinal cord, inhibiting the transmission of C and A δ fibers. This action enhances potassium conductance and intensifies the conduction blockade induced by local anesthetics.[6] It can be administered through multiple routes, including oral, transdermal, intravenous, perineural, or neuraxial.[6] Research indicates that administering less than 150 μ g of clonidine can significantly extend the anesthetic and analgesic effects of bupivacaine in a dose-dependent manner. It prolongs both sensory and motor block while promoting sedation; however, it may also lead to increased hypotension and bradycardia when introduced into the spinal space.[7] Previous studies utilizing higher doses of clonidine (150 mcg) intrathecally have been linked to hemodynamic instability and systemic side effects, despite the improved analgesic outcomes. Therefore, the objective of the present study was to evaluate the efficacy of two different doses of clonidine i.e. 30 mcg and 15 mcg as an adjunct to bupivacaine for spinal anesthesia in infraumbilical surgical procedures.

Material & Methods

This randomized double-blinded study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology at our tertiary care hospital from February 2023 to June 2024. Seventy patients aged 20 to 55 years with ASA I and II status scheduled for elective infraumbilical surgeries were recruited for this study. Patients with renal or hepatic dysfunction, those who are hemodynamically unstable, and individuals with allergies to the study drugs were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from the participants of the study. Institutional ethical clearance was secured for the study.

The patients were randomly allocated into two groups:

Group I - 12.5 mg, 0.5% bupivacaine (2.5 ml) + 15 mcg intrathecal clonidine (0.5 ml) (BC15)

Group II - 12.5 mg, 0.5% bupivacaine (2.5 ml) + 30 mcg intrathecal clonidine (0.5 ml) (BC30)

Total 35 patients in each group received 3 ml of the study drug.

The study was double-blinded, as the anaesthetist who prepared the drug was different from the one who collected the data. A comprehensive preanaesthetic evaluation was conducted. All pertinent investigations were conducted and assessed. Patients were kept NPO (nil per oral) for six hours prior to surgery. They received premedication with a 0.25 mg alprazolam tablet and a 40 mg pantoprazole capsule orally the night before surgery. On the day of surgery,

premedication was administered with an intravenous injection of ondansetron at a dosage of 0.10 to 0.15 mg/kg and an intravenous injection of ranitidine at a dosage of 4-8 mg/kg and injection ceftriaxone 25-30 mg/kg i.v. after conducting a sensitivity test. Baseline parameters, including heart rate (HR), systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP), SpO₂, and respiratory rate, were documented. After establishing an 18-gauge intravenous line, all patients were preloaded with 10 ml/kg of crystalloid solution.

Under aseptic conditions, spinal anesthesia was administered at the L3-L4 or L2-L3 level in a seated position via a midline approach using a 25-gauge Quincke spinal needle. After confirming the free flow of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), the study drug was administered making sure of negative aspiration of blood. Sensory block and motor block were evaluated every minute by testing for loss of sensation to a pinprick and by utilizing the modified Bromage score, respectively. Hemodynamic parameters were continuously monitored, i.e. respiratory rate, heart rate, non-invasive systolic and diastolic blood pressure, SpO₂, and electrocardiogram.

The operation commenced once surgical anesthesia (up to the T6 sensory dermatome) was established. In the event of a failed or partial neuraxial block, the patient was administered general anesthesia and subsequently excluded from the study. Events such as hypotension, bradycardia, sedation, and others were documented. Bradycardia was treated with an intravenous injection of atropine sulfate as per heart rate requirements. Hypotension was managed with intravenous administration of ephedrine and an additional Ringer's lactate solution.

Postoperative analgesia was evaluated using the visual analog scale (VAS) with a 0-10 cm range. Patients were informed about the VAS scale one day prior to surgery. If VAS > 4, inj. Diclofenac 75 mg was provided as rescue analgesia. The duration of analgesia for the study drug was defined as the period from the administration of the study drug to the administration of rescue analgesic (VAS > 4). The hemodynamic parameters and the number of significant events (bradycardia, hypotension, sedation) were documented and analyzed for comparison.

Statistical analysis

Data was collected and compiled using Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. The continuous data were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation. Frequency, percentage, means, and standard deviations (SD) were calculated for continuous variables, while ratios and proportions were determined for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically

significant. To assess the significance of two means, the Student's t-test was employed.

Results

The study recruited 70 participants and randomly allocated them into Group I and Group II. The two groups were comparable with respect to baseline demographic characteristics. There were 39 males and 31 females. (Table 1) There was no statistically significant difference in type of infraumbilical surgical procedures between the two groups.

Surgical procedures performed were fracture fixation lower limbs, caesarean section, hysterectomy. The mean time for the onset of sensory and motor block in group II was less than group I ($p < 0.05$). The mean duration of analgesia of group II was significantly higher than group I. (Table 2) The mean VAS score were lower at every follow-up in group II as compared to group I. The VAS score showed significant difference at every follow-up except at 15 and 30 minutes of enrolled patients. (Graph 1)

Table 1: Shows the Patient demographics and Mean duration of the surgery

Parameters	Group I	Group II	P value
Age(yrs)	45.22±11.79	43.42±10.28	>0.05
Weight(kg)	68.33±10.35	65.45±9.68	>0.05
Males	19	16	>0.05
Females	11	14	
Mean duration of the surgery (min)	114.55±37.64	124.32±43.81	>0.05

Table 2: Shows the Onset of sensory and motor block and duration of analgesia

Parameters	Group I (Mean±SD)	Group II (Mean±SD)	P value
Onset of sensory block (seconds)	179.49±42.31	161.47±36.22	<0.05
Onset of motor block (seconds)	204.52±15.67	192.34±11.45	<0.05
Duration of analgesia (min)	307.62±19.55	320.75±28.31	<0.05

Higher sedation scores were observed in Group II than in Group I ($p < 0.05$). Other side effects reported were hypotension, bradycardia and dryness of mouth which were comparable in both

the groups with no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

Graph 1 Shows the Postoperative VAS pain scores in Group I and Group II

Discussion

In the present study, baseline parameters were comparable in both the groups with no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). No significant difference was observed with respect to the type of surgeries and mean duration of surgery.

The onset of sensory block and onset of motor

block was earlier in Group II with 30mcg clonidine which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This is in accordance with the study conducted by Kaliya P 2023 which showed similar results.[3] Hyndavi K Sri et al compared two groups, patients were administered 0.25mcg clonidine in Group I and 0.05mcg clonidine in Group II. The study observed, the mean duration of sensory block in group I to be

313.48 ± 28.04 minutes & in group II to be 320.1 ± 26.85 minutes.[9] In contrast, study by Bhushan et al 2012 which compared three different doses of intrathecal clonidine 15mcg,30mcg and 60 mcg was not able to appreciate any dose dependent variation in onset of sensory block (0.90±0.29 min;0.95±0.30 min & 0.91±0.17 min) respectively. The onset of motor block observed was (1.48 ± 0.71 min: 1.59 ±0.52 min:1.71 ± 0.51 min) in the respective groups. However there was a dose dependent variation in duration of analgesia.[10]

In the present study, mean duration of analgesia was more in Group II with 30mcg clonidine as compared to Group I with 15 mcg which was statistically significant (p<0.05). This is in accordance with the study conducted by Kaliya P 2023 which showed similar results.3 In a study conducted by Shilpashri A. M et al. the mean duration of analgesia was 240.8 minutes in clonidine group (30µg).[11] Accordingly study by Bhushan et al 2012 also find a duration of analgesia to be significantly higher in bupivacaine clonidine 30mcg group (436.65 ± 149.84 min) than in bupivacaine clonidine 15 mcg group (387.1 ± 97.05 min) (p<0.01).10 Saxena H et al[12] and Strelbel et al[13] in nonobstetric surgery and by Bajwa SJ et al [6] in caesarean section surgery.

Clonidine enhances the sensory block in spinal anesthesia through presynaptic mechanisms (inhibiting neurotransmitter release) and postsynaptic effects (promoting hyperpolarization). When combined with bupivacaine, clonidine extends the postoperative pain-free period, which patients highly appreciate. These properties make clonidine particularly beneficial for lengthy procedures like repeat cesarean sections. Roh et al. recently proposed that the increased effectiveness of intrathecal clonidine in a rat model of neuropathic pain may be due to its ability to inhibit the phosphorylation of the NMDA receptor subunit NR1 in spinal dorsal horn neurons.[14]

In the present study, VAS scores were higher at every follow-up in group I .The postoperative pain relief was satisfactory in all patients. In Hyndavi K Sri et al study, there is no significant statistical difference in the visual analogue score of the patients in group-I in comparison with VAS in group-II recorded at 0 hours, 1 hour, 2 hours and 4 hours after giving spinal anaesthesia.[9]

In the present study, mean Ramsay sedation score was higher in group II as compared to Group I at all time intervals except at 12 hrs. In Kalia et al study 100% patients in bupivacaine heavy 12.5 mg +30 mcg of clonidine group were sedated with no requirement of active intervention. Other side effects were hypotension, bradycardia, and dryness of the mouth.[3] However, statistically, a non significant difference was observed between both

the groups. Similarly, Bhushan et al study, observed a dose dependent variability in sedation also. Higher sedation scores were noted in bupivacaine 60 mcg clonidine group than in bupivacaine 30 mcg of clonidine group than in bupivacaine 15 mcg of clonidine group (p<0.05).[4] Kothari N et al [15] also found 35 to 45 % patients drowsy by addition of 50 µg of clonidine to bupivacaine; but Bajwa SJ et al [6] did not find any sedation by addition of up to 45 µg of clonidine to bupivacaine. Thus, the sedation with clonidine was dose dependent.

Conclusion

The incorporation of intrathecal clonidine to bupivacaine during spinal anaesthesia, at 15 µg and 30 µg doses, significantly accelerates the onset of both sensory and motor block, elongates the duration of surgical analgesia, extends the duration of high-quality postoperative analgesia, and decreases the need for postoperative analgesics while maintaining relative hemodynamic stability. A dosage of 30 mcg of intrathecal clonidine yields optimal benefits with minimal adverse effects & is recommended for cases where an extension of spinal anesthesia is necessary, such as in patients undergoing extensive lower abdominal or lower limb surgeries.

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